

Appendix B - Table with descriptive statistics

Test	Unit of measure	N	Mean	SD	Coefficient of variation	Min	Max	Maximum possible score (closed scales only)
Test 1. MT reading test (reading time)	time per word (s)	129	0.50	0.11	0.21	0.35	0.95	
Test 1. MT reading test (accuracy)	number of errors	129	5.9	4.9	0.83	0.0	34.0	n.a.
Test 2. RAN colours	time per item (s)	129	0.78	0.16	0.21	0.46	1.30	
Test 3. RAN digits	time per item (s)	129	0.50	0.12	0.24	0.32	1.00	
Test 4. Orthographic decoding: Visual-visual Pseudo-word Matching	number of errors	129	2.4	3.7	1.59	0.0	27.0	90
Test 5. Orthographic decoding: Visual-auditory Pseudo-word Matching	number of errors	129	5.1	5.4	1.05	0.0	35.0	90
Test 6. Orthographic decoding: Auditory-auditory Pseudo-word Matching	number of errors	129	7.6	5.4	0.72	1.0	28.0	90
Test 7. "Nonna Concetta" Spelling-to-dictation	number of errors	129	2.8	2.2	0.81	0.0	12.0	n.a.
Test 8. Single Pseudo-word Repetition	number of correct items	129	16.0	4.4	0.27	4.0	25.0	30
Test 9. Single Pseudo-word Phonemic Segmentation	number of correct segmentations	129	187.9	23.0	0.12	116.0	223.0	239
Test 10. Orthographic Decision	number of errors	129	17.8	7.1	0.40	3.0	33.0	80
Test 11. Repetition of Pseudo-word Series	number of correct items	129	18.7	5.2	0.28	4.0	28.0	30
Test 13. Written Arithmetic Calculations	time per item (s)	129	41.8	12.9	0.31	17.5	90.9	
Test 12-13. Mental and Written Arithmetic Calculations	number of errors	129	2.7	1.8	0.67	0.0	8.0	14
Test 14. Dictation of Numbers	number of errors	89	0.4	1.0	2.75	0.0	8.0	8
Test 15. Arabic Number Reading test	number of errors	129	1.6	1.7	1.04	0.0	8.0	16
Test 16. Number Order test	number of errors	129	1.6	1.3	0.82	0.0	7.0	10
Test 17. Arithmetic Facts test	number of correct items	129	13.2	3.0	0.23	1.0	16.0	16
Test 18. Computation Strategies test	number of correct items	129	12.6	3.3	0.26	4.0	16.0	16
Test 19. Computation Procedures (Tabulation and carry)	number of errors	129	2.1	2.3	1.07	0.0	9.0	14
Test 20. Backward Counting	number of errors	129	1.0	1.1	1.11	0.0	5.0	49
Test 21. Symbol Search subtest	number of correct items	129	27.4	4.1	0.15	16.0	39.0	45
Test 22. Raven's Coloured Progressive Matrices	number of correct items	129	32.1	2.7	0.08	24.0	36.0	36
Test 23. Forward Span of Numbers	span length (number of digits)	129	5.0	0.9	0.17	4.0	7.0	9
Test 23. Backward Span of Numbers	span length (number of digits)	129	3.7	0.9	0.26	2.0	7.0	8
Test 24. Verbal Phonemic Fluency test	number of correct items	129	30.6	8.8	0.29	10.0	55.0	n.a.

n.a.: not applicable

Appendix C - Intercorrelations table

Pearson correlation matrix	Test 1. MT reading test (reading time)	Test 1. MT reading test (accuracy)	Test 2. RAN colours	Test 3. RAN digits	Test 4. Orthographic decoding: Visual - visual Pseudo-word Matching	Test 5. Orthographic decoding: Visual-auditory Pseudo-word Matching	Test 6. Orthographic decoding: Auditory-auditory Pseudo-word Matching	Test 7. "Nonna Concetta" Spelling-to-dictation	Test 8. Single Pseudo-word Repetition	Test 9. Single Pseudo-word Phonemic Segmentation	Test 10. Orthographic Decision	Test 11. Repetition of Pseudo-word Series	Test 13. Written Arithmetic Calculations	Test 12-13. Mental and Written Arithmetic Calculations	Test 14. Dictation of Numbers	Test 15. Arabic Number Reading test	Test 16. Number Order test	Test 17. Arithmetic Facts test	Test 18. Computation Strategies test	Test 19. Computation Procedures (Tabulation and carry)	Test 20. Backward Counting	Test 21. Symbol Search subtest	Test 22. Raven's Coloured Progressive Matrices	Test 23. Forward Span of Numbers	Test 23. Backward Span of Numbers	Test 24. Verbal Phonemic Fluency test
Test 1. MT reading test (reading time)	1	.301**	.394**	.406**	.255**	.443**	.252**	.299**	-.283**	-.336**	.542**	-.429**	.534**	.346**	.000	.308**	.244**	-.541**	-.477**	.130	.181*	-.291**	-.232**	-.254**	-.249**	-.287**
Test 1. MT reading test (accuracy)	.301**	1	.080	.015	.303**	.175*	.082	.287**	-.036	-.263**	.285**	-.301**	.126	.226**	.055	.212*	.135	-.185*	-.223*	.020	.427**	-.294**	-.235**	-.139	-.262**	.085
Test 2. RAN colours	.394**	.080	1	.709**	.083	.264**	.080	.063	-.247**	-.100	.118	-.268**	.327**	.175*	-.059	.159	.223*	-.423**	-.175*	.322**	.056	-.300**	-.244**	-.159	-.118	-.365**
Test 3. RAN digits	.406**	.015	.709**	1	.031	.225*	.015	-.037	-.277**	-.042	.012	-.134	.391**	.039	-.128	.000	.030	-.470**	-.131	.296**	-.064	-.312**	-.006	-.220*	-.085	-.353**
Test 4. Orthographic decoding: Visual-auditory Pseudo-word Matching	.255**	.303**	.083	.031	1	.320**	.373**	.182*	-.043	-.245**	.348**	-.079	.171	.186**	-.001	.205*	.125	-.289**	-.157	.141	.230**	-.147	-.264**	-.075	-.237**	-.113
Test 5. Orthographic decoding: Visual-auditory Pseudo-word Matching	.443**	.175*	.264**	.225*	.320**	1	.641**	.081	-.526**	-.476**	.347**	-.438**	.285**	.278**	-.029	.218*	.161	-.463**	-.175*	.112	.056	-.241**	-.286**	-.170	-.257**	-.236**
Test 6. Orthographic decoding: Auditory-auditory Pseudo-word Matching	.252**	.082	.080	.015	.373**	.641**	1	.072	-.429**	-.361**	.273**	-.287**	.241**	.323**	.000	.152	.157	-.282**	-.140	.176*	-.060	-.141	-.241**	-.220*	-.135	-.153
Test 7. "Nonna Concetta" Spelling-to-dictation	.299**	.287**	.063	-.037	.182*	.081	.072	1	.031	-.115	.451**	-.347**	.222*	.340**	.129	.207*	.367**	-.318**	-.282**	.034	.239**	.010	-.237**	-.061	-.130	-.040
Test 8. Single Pseudo-word Repetition	-.283**	-.036	-.247**	-.277**	-.043	-.526**	-.429**	.031	1	.608**	-.230**	.479**	-.206*	-.127	.051	-.089	-.198*	.397**	.080	-.166	.136	.199*	.286**	.206*	.118	.318**
Test 9. Single Pseudo-word Phonemic Segmentation	-.336**	-.263**	-.100	-.042	-.245**	-.476**	-.361**	-.115	.608**	1	-.296**	.592**	-.106	-.247**	-.090	-.239**	-.245**	.336**	.124	.000	-.079	.093	.375**	.206*	.288**	.224*
Test 10. Orthographic Decision	.542**	.285**	.118	.012	.348**	.347**	.273**	.451**	-.230**	-.296**	1	-.413**	.408**	.417**	.159	.323**	.495**	-.518**	-.428**	.017	.244**	-.195*	-.352**	-.140	-.293**	-.273**
Test 11. Repetition of Pseudo-word Series	-.429**	-.301**	-.268**	-.134	-.079	-.438**	-.287**	-.347**	.479**	.592**	-.413**	1	-.185*	-.323**	.002	-.243**	-.388**	.380**	.271**	-.090	-.146	.255**	.422**	.249**	.370**	.293**
Test 13. Written Arithmetic Calculations	.534**	.126	.327**	.391**	.171	.285**	.241**	.222*	-.206*	-.106	.408**	-.185*	1	.389**	.059	.294**	.281**	-.570**	-.418**	.179*	.028	-.298**	-.037	-.197*	-.186*	-.259**
Test 12-13. Mental and Written Arithmetic Calculations	.346**	.226**	.175*	.039	.186*	.278**	.323**	.340**	-.127	-.247**	.417**	-.323**	.389**	1	.124	.290**	.372**	-.391**	-.427**	.142	.100	-.154	-.336**	-.147	-.162	-.062
Test 14. Dictation of Numbers	.066	.024	-.027	-.114	.008	.107	.134	.119	-.092	-.168	.247*	-.068	.168	.192	1	.413**	.255*	-.258*	-.149	.024	.275**	.000	-.239*	-.117	-.059	.075
Test 15. Arabic Number Reading test	.308**	.212*	.159	.000	.205*	.218*	.152	.207*	-.089	-.239**	.323**	-.243**	.294**	.290**	.365**	1	.252**	-.344**	-.246**	-.016	.241**	-.060	-.299**	-.043	-.215*	-.122
Test 16. Number Order test	.244**	.135	.223*	.030	.125	.161	.157	.367**	-.198*	-.245**	.495**	-.388**	.281**	.372**	.173*	.252**	1	-.361**	-.388**	.051	.177*	-.115	-.448**	.014	-.111	-.236**

Test 17. Arithmetic Facts test	-.541**	-.185*	-.423**	-.470**	-.289**	-.463**	-.282**	-.318**	.397**	.336**	-.518**	.380**	-.570**	-.391**	-.051	-.344**	-.361**	1	.352**	-.302**	-.124	.270**	.196*	.177*	.224*	.376**
Test 18. Computation Strategies test	-.477**	-.223*	-.175*	-.131	-.157	-.175*	-.140	-.282**	.080	.124	-.428**	.271**	-.418**	-.427**	-.074	-.246**	-.388**	.352**	1	-.116	-.160	.357**	.351**	.108	.196*	.239**
Test 19. Computation Procedures (Tabulation and carry)	.130	.020	.322**	.296**	.141	.112	.176*	.034	-.166	.000	.017	-.090	.179*	.142	-.042	-.016	.051	-.302**	-.116	1	-.033	-.141	-.116	-.064	-.063	-.135
Test 20. Backward Counting	.181*	.427**	.056	-.064	.230**	.056	-.060	.239**	.136	-.079	.244**	-.146	.028	.100	.290**	.241**	.177*	-.124	-.160	-.033	1	-.043	-.225*	-.101	-.137	.098
Test 21. Symbol Search subtest	-.291**	-.294**	-.300**	-.312**	-.147	-.241**	-.141	.010	.199*	.093	-.195*	.255**	-.298**	-.154	.038	-.060	-.115	.270**	.357**	-.141	-.043	1	.143	.115	.321**	.303**
Test 22. Raven's Coloured Progressive Matrices	-.232**	-.235**	-.244**	-.006	-.264**	-.286**	-.241**	-.237**	.286**	.375**	-.352**	.422**	-.037	-.336**	-.164	-.299**	-.448**	.196*	.351**	-.116	-.225*	.143	1	.087	.275**	.196*
Test 23. Forward Span of Numbers	-.254**	-.139	-.159	-.220*	-.075	-.170	-.220*	-.061	.206*	.206*	-.140	.249**	-.197*	-.147	-.103	-.043	.014	.177*	.108	-.064	-.101	.115	.087	1	.231**	.084
Test 23. Backward Span of Numbers	-.249**	-.262**	-.118	-.085	-.237**	-.257**	-.135	-.130	.118	.288**	-.293**	.370**	-.186*	-.162	-.022	-.215*	-.111	.224*	.196*	-.063	-.137	.321**	.275**	.231**	1	.218*
Test 24. Verbal Phonemic Fluency test	-.287**	.085	-.365**	-.353**	-.113	-.236**	-.153	-.040	.318**	.224*	-.273**	.293**	-.259**	-.062	.137	-.122	-.236**	.376**	.239**	-.135	.098	.303**	.196*	.084	.218*	1

** p 0,01 (two-tailed).

* p 0,05 (two-tailed).